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CONSUMER AWARENESS ON PROCTER AND GAMBLE PRODUCTS - A STUDY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE AT TIRUNELVELI

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Abstract

Consumer awareness is important so that purchaser can take the accurate decision and make the exact choice. FMCG sector is a very important contributor to India's Gross Domestic Product. It has been contributing to the demand of lower and middle income groups in India. Consumer Awareness is an act of building positive thoughts that the buyer or consumer is conscious of the information about products, goods, services, and consumers' rights.

Keywords: Consumer Awareness , P&G , FMCG

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Consumer Awareness is an act of building positive thoughts that the buyer or consumer is conscious of the information about products, goods, services, and consumers rights. Consumer awareness is important so that purchaser can take the accurate decision and make the exact choice.

1.2 REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Surinder S. K. (2013) The author has studied the consumers' perception towards the fast moving consumer goods in rural markets. The data are collected with the aid of well prepared questionnaire from 1000 respondents among 40 villages in Haryana state. The results show that the rural buyers perceived that TV commercials followed by print advertisements and word of mouth plays a significant role for taking the decision to purchase these FMCGs and rural buyers perceived that social factors are no so strong that those may influence their decision to purchase these FMCGs.

Srivastava and Kumar (2013) analysed that FMCG sector is a vital contributor to India's Gross Domestic Product. It has been contributing to the demand of lower and middleincome groups in India. Over 73% of FMCG products are sold to middle class households in which over 52% is in rural India. Rural marketing has become the hottest marketing arena for most of the FMCG companies. The rural India market is enormous and the opportunities are unlimited. This research paper provides detailed analysis about the contribution of FMCG industry in growth of Indian rural market and aims to discuss about customer attitude towards better purchasing

decision for FMCG products in rural market with growing awareness and brand consciousness among people across various socio-economic classes in rural market.

1.3 OBJECTIVES

Below are the objectives of the present study

- To know the socio-economic profile of consumers purchasing Procter & Gamble products.
- To know the awareness and attitude of consumers on purchasing Procter & Gamble products.
- To know the satisfactory level of respondents on their purchase of Procter and gamble products.
- To make finding based on the study and provide suitable suggestion to improve their purchase on fast moving consumers goods.

1.4 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study on “CONSUMER AWARENESS ON PROCTER AND GAMBLE PRODUCTS” covers the geographical area of Tirunelveli city. The main aim of the study is to find out the consumer awareness of Procter and Gamble product among the Tirunelveli people.

1.5 SAMPLE SIZE OF RESPONDENT

100 respondent of sample size

1.6 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

Simple random sampling technique was used for collect the primary data.

1.7 AREA OF STUDY

Tirunelveli.

1.8 PERIOD OF STUDY

Period of study covers from December 2018 to March 2019.

1.9 METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

1.9.1 Primary Data

The primary data collected through questionnaire administered to a sample of 100 consumers selected from Tirunelveli. The questionnaire was pre-designed and pre-tested before it was administered.

1.9.2 Secondary Data

Secondary data was collected through various publications of newspaper, magazines, books and magazines.

1.10 STATISTICAL TOOL USED

After data was collected a master table was prepared. Modern statistical tools are used a research work. Percentage, Liker’s 5 rating scale and Garrett ranking technique were used for analyzing the data.

1.11 LIMITAIONS OF THE STUDY

- ❖ The study is conducted only in Tirunelveli.

- ❖ The analysis made only with limited sample.
- ❖ The study aims at know the consumer awareness of P&G Product.
- ❖ Term duration for conducting research is very limited due to lack of time extensive research is not conducted.

1.12 DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

TABLE NO:1.1

DEMOGRAPHIC DETAILS OF SAMPLE RESPONDENTS

AGEWISE DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLE RESPONDENTS			
S.No.	Age	No. of respondent	Percentage
1.	Below 20	52	52
2.	21 – 30	36	36
3.	31 – 40	8	8
4.	Above 41	4	4
	Total	100	100
GENDER WISE DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLE RESPONDENTS			
S.No.	Gender	No. of Respondent	Percentage
1.	Male	22	22
2.	Female	78	78
	Total	100	100
OCCUPATION OF SAMPLE RESPONDENTS			
S.No	Occupation	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Businessmen	13	13
2	Government Employees	16	16
3	Private Employees	31	31
4	Professionals	24	24
5	House Wives	7	7
6	Students	9	9
	Total	100	100
MONTHLY INCOME			

S.No	Monthly Income	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Below Rs.10,000	22	22
2.	Rs.10,001 – Rs.20,000	25	25
3.	Rs.20,001 – Rs.30,000	18	18
4.	Rs.30,001 – Rs.40,000	16	16
5.	Above Rs.40,001	29	29
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

Above table shows that the demographic profile of sample respondents ie their age, gender, occupation and their income of respondents at Tirunelveli. These factors are vitally influenced their purchase, therefore, those are taken for the study.

1.12.1 AWARENESS AND SOURCES OF AWARENESS

Knowing about the awareness of P&G brands is more important for the present study. Hence it is collected and presented in table no 1.2. People could know the information through media, friends and relatives. Internet and online advertising also play vital role for their choice on purchase.

TABLE 1.2.AWARENESS OF P&G PRODUCTS

S.No	Awareness of P&G Products	No of Respondent	Percentage
1	Aware	65	65
2	Not Aware	35	35
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

The analysis shows that 65 percentage of the respondents are aware of P & G product while 35 percentage are not aware of it though they are attracted at its brand name.

TABLE 1.3.SOURCE OF INFORMATION

S.No	Source	No of Respondent	Percentage
1	Advertisement	27	27
2	Friends	40	40
3	Relatives	14	14
4	Internet	19	19
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

The study says that 27 percentages of the respondents know about the product through Advertisements, 40 percentages of the respondents through Friends, 14 percentages of the respondents through Relatives and 19 percentages through Internet.

It is inferred that 40 percentages of the respondents know about the product through Friends.

TABLE 1.4.LOYALTY ON P&G PRODUCTS

S.No.	Regular customer	No. of Respondent	Percentage
1.	Regular purchasers	61	61
2.	Not regular purchasers	39	39
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table makes it very clear that 61 percentages of the respondents are the regular customer to P & G products and 39 percentages of the respondents are not.

It is inferred that 61 percentages of the respondents are the regular customers to P & G products.

1.12.2 CUSTOMERS' PREFERENCE

TABLE 1.5.PREFERENCE OF PROCTOR AND GAMBLE PRODUCTS

TYPE OF PRODUCTS PREFERRED			
S.No	Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Household care	26	26
2	Hygiene and Health care	44	44
3	Beauty Grooming& Hair care segments	30	30
	Total	100	100
BRAND PREFERENCE ON HYGIENE & HEALTH CARE PRODUCTS			
S.No	Preference on Hygiene & Health Care products	No. of Respondent	Percentage
1	Vicks	29	29
2	Whispher	24	24
3	Pampers	6	6
4	Oral-B	25	25
5	Ambipur	16	16
	Total	100	100
Brand preference on Hair Care Segment Products			
S.No	Products	No. of Respondent	Percentage
1	Pantene	33	33
2	Head & Shoulder	57	57
3	Wella	10	10
	Total	100	100
Brand Preference on Beauty Grooming Segment			
Sl.No	Products	No. of respondent	Percentage
1	Gillette	31	31
2	Olay	49	49

Total	100	100
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Source: Primary Data

The table no shows the preference of proctor and gamble products by the respondents. Vicks preference high in health care segments and followed by oral – B. Under hair care segments people preferred head and shoulders. In Beauty grooming, they preferred to buy Olay.

1.12.3 SATISFACTION ON P&G PRODUCTS

TABLE 1.6.SATISFACTION ON P&G PRODUCTS

S. No.	Variables	H.S	S	N	D	H.D	Weighted Scores	Weighted Mean Scores
1.	Satisfaction with the quality of products	120	144	54	20	12	350	3.50
2.	Satisfaction with availability of products	125	116	63	26	12	342	3.42
3.	Satisfaction with price	105	92	90	64	10	361	3.61
4.	Satisfaction on Opinions given by others on themselves	90	108	57	46	13	314	3.14
5.	Availability of Products	100	104	75	38	10	327	3.27
6.	Advertisement for P&G products	110	132	48	36	11	337	3.37
7.	Satisfaction on brands of P&G	120	108	78	32	12	350	3.50

Source: Primary Data

This analysis shows the satisfaction on proctor and gambles products and it weighted score and mean scores.

1.12.4 PREFERENCE ON VARIOUS BRANDS OF P&G PRODUCTS

Below table shows the choice of household care products and its ranks particularly on washing powder. Their preference on usage of various brands on Beauty grooming and health care segments.

TABLE 1.7.Choice of household care products

Sl.No	Household care products	Weighted Garrett Value	Weighted Average Garrett Value	Rank
1.	Tide	5574	55.74	II
2.	Gain	5103	51.03	III
3.	Ariel	6327	63.27	I
4.	Duracell	4739	47.39	IV
5	Mr. Clean	4576	45.76	V
6.	Dawn	4323	43.23	VI

Source: Computed from primary data

On the basis of Garret Ranking method choice on washing powder was ranked by respondents. First rank goes to Ariel, Second rank goes to Tide, Third rank goes to Gain, Fourth rank goes to Duracell, Fifth rank goes to Mr. Clean and Sixth rank goes to Dawn.

TABLE 1.8.CHOICE ON BEAUTY GROOMING PRODUCTS

Sl.No	Beauty Grooming products	Weighted Garrett Value	Weighted Average Garrett Value	Rank
1.	Gillette	4975	49.75	III
2.	Olay	5474	54.74	I
3.	Fusion	5020	50.20	II
4.	Wella	4822	48.22	IV

Source: Computed from primary data

Based on analysis it is clear that most preferable brand is Olay followed by Fusion. Least preference is wella.

TABLE 1.9.CHOICE OF HEALTH CARE SEGMENT

Sl.No	Health care segment	Weighted Garrett Value	Weighted Average Garrett Value	Rank
1.	Pampers	5102	51.02	IV
2.	Pantene	5483	53.83	III
3.	Crest	4990	49.90	V
4.	Oral – B	5756	57.56	II
5.	Head & Shoulder	5757	57.57	I
6.	Bounty	4522	45.22	VII
7.	Whisper	4984	49.84	VI

Source: Computed from primary data

Based on analysis it is clear that most preferable brand is Head&Shoulders followed by Oral - B. Pamper and whisper secured IV and VI rank. Least preference is Bounty.

1.12.5 INFLUENCING FACTORS

TABLE 1.10.FACTORS CONSIDERED AT THE TIME OF PURCHASE

Sl.No	Brand Image	Weighted Garrett Value	Weighted Average Garrett Value	Rank
1.	Price	5441	54.41	II
2.	Promotion	4878	48.78	V
3.	Package	4985	49.85	IV
4.	Brand name	5456	54.56	I
5.	Quality	5313	53.13	III
6.	Availability	4515	45.15	VI

Source: Computed from primary data

On the basis of Garret Ranking First rank goes to Brand Name , Second rank goes to Price, Third rank goes to Quality, Fourth rank goes to Package, Fifth rank goes to Promotion and sixth rank goes to Availability.

1.13 FINDINGS, SUGGESTION AND CONCLUSION

The findings and suggestions are discussed in a concise manner rather than descriptive form.

1.13.1 FINDINGS

- 52% of the respondents were below the age of 20 years.
- 78% of the respondents were Female.
- 41% of respondents are Under Graduate.
- 83% of respondents are Unmarried.
- 31% of respondents are Private Employee.
- 73% of the respondents belong to a nuclear family.
- 29% earn above Rs.40,000 per month.
- 65% of the respondents are aware of P & G product.
- 40% of the respondents came to know about the product through their Friends.
- 61% of the respondents are the regular customer of P & G products.
- 38% of the respondents used to spend between Rs.1001 – Rs.2000.
- 33% of the respondents are motivated to buy the products by celebrity.
- 68% of the respondents say they do not face any problems.
- 44% of the respondents prefer 'Hygiene and Health care' category.
- 67% of the respondents purchased in Super market.
- 29% of the respondents prefer Vicks.
- 57% of the respondents use Head & Shoulder.
- 49% of the respondents buy Olay.

- It is found that the respondents have ranked Brand Name as first, followed by price, Quality, Package, Promotion and Availability for the factors influencing on their purchase.

1.13.2 SUGGESTIONS

- Due to over usage of chemicals, many of the respondents say that they face side effect and some problem. Hence, usage of chemicals should be reduced as minimum or better to concentrate on introducing organic products.
- Despite constant advertising and publicity, consumers are still unaware of P&G products. The company can pay more attention towards advertisement on its company name.
- Consumers prefer best quality products at any price, so the company can introduce products under beauty & Grooming segment. Herbal ingredients can be highlighted more in beauty products as much as possible in other segments too.

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